

The questionnaire used in Test 2

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Assessment of KSO Chatbot

With the help of the word pairs please enter what you consider the most appropriate description for **KSO Chatbot**.

Please click one item in every line.

stylish*	<input type="radio"/>	tacky						
predictable*	<input type="radio"/>	unpredictable						
cheap*	<input type="radio"/>	premium						
alienating*	<input type="radio"/>	integrating						
brings me closer to people*	<input type="radio"/>	separates me from people						
unpresentable*	<input type="radio"/>	presentable						
rejecting*	<input type="radio"/>	inviting						
unimaginative*	<input type="radio"/>	creative						
good*	<input type="radio"/>	bad						

* required field

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Please click one item in every line.

human*	<input type="radio"/>	technical						
isolating*	<input type="radio"/>	connective						
pleasant*	<input type="radio"/>	unpleasant						
inventive*	<input type="radio"/>	conventional						
simple*	<input type="radio"/>	complicated						
professional*	<input type="radio"/>	unprofessional						
ugly*	<input type="radio"/>	attractive						
practical*	<input type="radio"/>	impractical						
likeable*	<input type="radio"/>	disagreeable						
cumbersome*	<input type="radio"/>	straightforward						

* required field

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Assessment of **KSO Chatbot**

With the help of the word pairs please enter what you consider the most appropriate description for **KSO Chatbot**.

Please click one item in every line.

confusing*	<input type="radio"/>	clearly structured						
repelling*	<input type="radio"/>	appealing						
bold*	<input type="radio"/>	cautious						
innovative*	<input type="radio"/>	conservative						
dull*	<input type="radio"/>	captivating						
undemanding*	<input type="radio"/>	challenging						
motivating*	<input type="radio"/>	discouraging						
novel*	<input type="radio"/>	ordinary						
unruly*	<input type="radio"/>	manageable						

* required field

Full result from test 2 provided by the AttrakDiff calculator platform at <http://www.attrakdiff.de/index-en.html>

The mean values of the word pairs are presented here. Of particular interest are the extreme values. These show which characteristics are particularly critical or particularly well-resolved. The blue color stands for chatbot A, while the orange line represents chatbot B.

The portfolio provided by the AttrakDiff framework in test 2

The AttrakDiff framework provides additional insights into the interactive nature of each version. The analysis highlights the result portfolio of each version in the forms of confidence rectangles across a vertical axis of HQ and on the horizontal axis of PQ. The blue rectangle represents chatbot version A while the orange one represents chatbot version B in the figure above. The smaller the confidence rectangles are, the less coincidental the result is. Similarly, larger rectangles are less significant because they may involve many regions on the graph (e.g., ‘desired’ or ‘self-oriented’). The Confidence rectangle of chatbot version A covers an area of ‘desired’ and ‘task-oriented’ while that of version B covers ‘neutral’ and slightly ‘task-oriented’. Accordingly, version A is preferred by the participants, which corresponds to a relatively high level of satisfaction, while the emotional perception of version B is neutral. ‘Task-oriented’ indicates that the users find both versions useful for task completion.